

Perspectives Of Secondary School Teachers On Curriculum Pacesetters: Balancing Coverage And Quality In Education

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Since the inception of democracy in South Africa, the government has consistently embarked on various initiatives with the primary goal of improving the quality of education and preparing students to excel in the global economy. One such initiative is the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS), orchestrated by the Department of Education. CAPS curriculum, through Annual Teaching Plans (ATP), prescribes specific timeframes within which teachers are expected to cover the curriculum, without taking into consideration the diverse learning abilities of the learners they teach. The focus of this study is to explore teachers' perspectives regarding the use of these "pace setters" to monitor curriculum coverage. To achieve this, the research adopted a qualitative methodology, employing a case study design. The study's participants were five English language teachers selected purposively from five secondary schools (Further Education Training Phase). The data were collected by using a semi-structured interview schedule. The findings showed that the prescribed pace for completing the curriculum was rigid and challenging for teachers. This inflexibility did not enhance teaching and learning standards. The challenge is especially pronounced when it comes to accommodating learners with varying abilities. The constant pressure to maintain this pace often results in a compromise on the quality of education delivery. Therefore, it can be suggested that the Department of Basic Education rethinks its approach and develops a curriculum that embraces flexibility and adaptability. Instead of rigidly adhering to a one-size-fits-all curriculum, schools should be granted the autonomy to engage in curriculum mapping and prioritize content based on their specific circumstances. This shift would help create a more conducive environment for effective teaching and learning, ensuring that students receive the education they truly need to succeed in a globalized world.

Key words: Curriculum Coverage; Quality Teaching And Learning; Pace Setting; Differentiated Abilities; School Contexts

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Introduction

Since the advent of democracy, the South African government has embarked on numerous endeavours with the objective of improving the standard of education and preparing learners for success in the international economic landscape. One of such efforts is Pace Setters. Curriculum pace setters, as it is affectionately known in South Africa, is an approach adopted by the Department of Basic Education in establishing guidelines for secondary school teachers to guarantee the comprehensive implementation of the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) by utilizing Annual Teaching Plans (Department of Education, 2012). Through the Annual Teaching Plans (ATP), specific timelines have been established for teachers to complete the curriculum, without taking into account the varying learning capabilities of learners. Teachers are compelled to move through the content at exactly the pace established (Hacoben&Weinshall, 2019; Lambrianos, 2019).

However, the predetermined timeframe for teachers to complete the curriculum has posed challenges. This timeline does not allow learners time to fully grasp concepts deepen their understanding and develop the skills needed in today's rapidly changing world (Naidoo, 2019). Critics argue that sticking to a pace, for covering the curriculum

hampers the delivery of quality education especially in South African secondary schools (Kosloski, 2019). This is because teachers often find themselves overly focused on meeting curriculum benchmarks at the expense of addressing elements.

The pressure to conform to curriculum deadlines leads teachers to hastily deliver content to learners (Ndebele et al., 2022). This rushed approach leaves time for teaching and consequently overwhelms many learners, particularly those with average or slower learning styles who struggle to keep up with the accelerated pace. The emphasis on achieving measurable curriculum objectives undermines the broader educational goal (Mpuangnan, 2024), contributing to a situation where the quantity of material takes precedence over the quality of learning experiences. The purpose of this study is to investigate and understand teachers' perspectives on various aspects related to the pace setters' approach to curriculum coverage for quality teaching and learning.

Pacesetter curriculum

The pacesetter curriculum offers a clear and organized approach to education (Lane, 2023), helping teachers cover all necessary content within a set timeframe while maintaining high teaching and learning standards. Mngomezulu (2023) points out that teachers view these curricula as vital tools to ensure that lessons align with educational standards, allowing them to cover the syllabus comprehensively and avoid missing crucial topics. Wolf (1995) adds that the "Pacesetter Initiative" aims to provide a more logical and well-ordered plan for delivering curriculum content. This kind of structured reform moves away from simply skimming through topics and instead promotes a deeper understanding, leading to more meaningful learning experiences.

The strength of the pacesetter curriculum lies in its flexibility, which allows it to be adapted to various educational settings. For example, Rozmus et al. (2014) showed its effectiveness in nursing education by creating uniform learning experiences across different clinical environments, ensuring students develop essential skills consistently. Jacobs (2018) also found that in personalized learning environments, the pacesetter model balances structure with flexibility, enhancing student engagement and learning success. Alemi and Sadehvandi (2012) explored its use in language learning through the "Pacesetter Series" textbooks, which provide a structured path for skill development. Given South Africa's ongoing efforts to reform education and improve quality (Khanyile & Mpuangnan, 2023), understanding teachers' views on this model could provide valuable insights for policymakers and educators. It could help adapt educational strategies to better meet the needs of students from different socio-economic backgrounds. This will ultimately foster more effective and inclusive learning environments.

Objectives

1. To establish how secondary school teachers view the effectiveness of the pace setters' approach in covering the curriculum.
2. To determine the contribution of pace setters to effective quality teaching.
3. To explore teachers' opinions on how the pace setters influence learners' academic achievement.

Theoretical framework

Goal setting theory propounded by John Locke and Latham (2020) and Curriculum Implementation theory founded by Gross, Giacquinta, and Bernstein (1971) were selected and adapted for this study, as they offered an applicable way to situate teachers' perspectives in context and to facilitate a systematic interpretation of the data. These theories provide a conceptual framework and practical guidance for understanding, analysing, and improving the process of curriculum implementation. They help in setting clear goals, motivating stakeholders, establishing feedback mechanisms, and ensuring that the implemented curriculum aligns with desired learning outcomes.

The principles of Goal Setting Theory emphasize the importance of setting clear objectives. In the context of the study, having clear goals such as understanding teachers' perspectives, assessing the effectiveness of the pace setters' approach, and exploring its impact on academic achievement provides a structured framework for the research. Goal Setting Theory suggests that clear and challenging goals can enhance motivation. By investigating teachers' perspectives and the effectiveness of the pace setters' approach, the study can identify factors that either motivate or demotivate teachers in the implementation of the curriculum. Understanding these motivational factors can contribute to better curriculum implementation. By exploring teachers' opinions on how the pace setters influence learners' academic achievement, the study can provide valuable feedback for educators and policymakers. This feedback can guide adjustments to the curriculum or instructional approaches to better align with the intended goals.

On the other hand, the curriculum implementation theory articulated by Gross et al. (1971) revolves around the intricate process of translating educational curricula into tangible classroom practices. It centres on the dynamic interplay of several vital components within the curriculum, including curriculum objectives, those responsible for implementation, the classroom environment, and the actual teaching and learning processes. To realize the intended educational outcomes delineated in a curriculum, it is vital to grasp the intricate relationships among these elements. Understanding teachers' perspectives in the study is essential for identifying potential challenges, concerns, or successes in the actual implementation of the curriculum.

Literature review

Effectiveness of the pace setters' approach in covering the curriculum

Many scholars argue that the time stipulated for curriculum coverage created a tension between the breadth and the depth of the curriculum (Hlophe, 2019; Moobola & Mulenga, 2020; Kazihla, 2020; Wafulal, Kisilu & Mukwa, 2019). This is because teachers often face challenges in covering the extensive curriculum within the limited time available, leading to a deficiency in pedagogical content knowledge for learners (Assuncao Flores & Gago, 2020). In many instances, adherence to CAPS directives fulfils accountability criteria but may not necessarily align with the curriculum's intended outcomes.

Snell and Cushing (2022) conducted a study, emphasizing the significance of classroom time regulation in educational policy. They found that policymakers prioritized the pace of teaching as a key indicator of effective education. A fast-teaching pace was considered synonymous with quality education. However, the rapid pace and limited time available for literacy lessons hindered the ability to teach more complex literacy skills and restricted students' independent thinking. The pressure to cover the curriculum within a specific timeframe created a tension between curriculum breadth and depth, with an inclination towards breadth rather than depth (Woo, 2023).

Mazenod, Francis, Archer, and Hodgen's study (2019) aligned with the findings of Snell and Cushing (2022) in the UK. They observed that teachers in the UK adjusted their teaching pace and content based on the abilities of their students. In this approach, students were divided into groups according to their skill levels. Higher-ability groups delved deeper into the subject matter, engaging in independent work over an extended period. In contrast, lower-ability groups received more repetition and practice on fundamental concepts. This method allowed teachers to tailor their instruction to help individual students achieve specific learning objectives by the end of each lesson.

Booyesen's (2018) study among secondary school teachers in Ennerdale, South Africa, reveals a desire for a more flexible implementation of the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS). The majority of teachers express the view that a flexible curriculum would better cater to diverse learning needs, fostering optimal performance. Booyesen (2018) argues against a one-size-fits-all approach, advocating for flexibility and collaborative teaching to accommodate diverse student needs and learning styles. The study suggests that adapting to students' individual requirements aligns with the overarching goal of providing quality education for all.

Contribution of pace setters to effective quality teaching

Garcia, Olsen and Simbaqueba (2021) emphasise that the quality of education plays a significant role in shaping how learners engage with the learning process. This suggests that the effectiveness of education hinges significantly on its quality. Also, Ulrich (2023) contends that within the educational community, there should be a concerted effort to prioritize learning experiences that empower learners to automatically apply acquired knowledge, skills, and attitudes. This entails fostering environments characterized by safety, comfort, and health, which are conducive to meaningful interactions and growth. In essence, both perspectives underscore the importance of not only the content delivered in education but also the manner in which it is imparted and the environment in which learning takes place. However, several scholars contend that the time constraints imposed on teaching pose a significant obstacle in schools, a point highlighted by scholars like Chogyel and Wangdi (2021) and Garcia-Morales, Garrido-Moreno & Martin-Rojas (2021). This limitation adversely affects learner performance by impeding practical, hands-on experiences crucial for understanding concepts. Letshwene and Du Plessis (2021) discovered that the dissatisfaction arising from an inability to cover the prescribed curriculum within allocated timeframes compels teachers to offer extra assistance beyond regular school hours. In Bhutan's Chhukha district, the challenge is specifically evident in 9th and 10th-grade Chemistry classes, prompting teachers to resort to video presentations to address the time deficit. This situation underscores the importance of considering the pedagogical aspects of teaching, emphasizing the negative impact of rigid timeframes on the learning process and student performance.

Influence of pacesetters curriculum on learners' academic achievement

Negative perceptions were that CAPS was too much of a "one-size-fits-all" policy and "a push me over" policy which dictates how fast can you move (Gouedard, Point, Hyttinen & Haug, 2020). According to Sebaeng (2022), teachers felt that their freedom was constrained by the pace set, saying that the prescriptive nature of CAPS hindered them from ensuring that all learners attained understanding and met the levels expected by assessments. The content and time prescriptions compelled teachers to focus on time rather than subject knowledge. Generally, the starting point for quality teaching and learning is the goal of ensuring that all learners have a full grasp of subject knowledge and can apply it in different contexts. Thus, content knowledge should be the priority rather than the pace at which it is conveyed. This discrepancy could be avoided if the curriculum were less densely packed with content.

The common thread in these studies is the tension between curriculum breadth and depth due to time constraints, as echoed by scholars like Hlophe (2019), Moobola & Mulenga (2020), Kazihla (2020), and Wafula, Kisilu & Mukwa (2019). The challenge lies in covering the extensive curriculum within a limited time, impacting pedagogical content knowledge. Adherence to rigid curriculum directives, such as CAPS, is seen as fulfilling accountability criteria but may not align with intended outcomes. Negative perceptions arise from the perceived one-size-fits-all nature of CAPS, hindering teachers' freedom and focusing on pace over subject knowledge. The discrepancy could be mitigated by reducing content density in the curriculum, allowing for a more nuanced and effective teaching approach.

Methodology

The research employed a qualitative approach to capture the viewpoints of secondary school teachers regarding the impacts of pace setters on curriculum coverage and the quality of teaching and learning. This study offered a chance to uncover the perspectives and opinions of the participants (Creswell, 2014; Palikans, Horwitz, Green, Wisdom & Duan, 2015).

Participants

Participants of the study include five secondary school English language teachers selected from five schools in King Cetshwayo district. While the schools were randomly selected, the participants were selected by using a purposive sampling technique. The selection was based on the knowledge and many years of teaching experience of the English language at the Further Education and Training (FET) phase. Therefore, the selected participants were given codes such as T1 for teacher 1, T2 for teacher 2, T3 for teacher 3, T4 for teacher 4 and T5 for teacher 5. To collect data from the participants, a semi-structured interview schedule was used.

The interview questions focused on understanding teachers' views on how the pace-setter approach affects curriculum coverage, quality of teaching, and students' academic performance. To make sure the questions were clear and effective, three education experts reviewed them for content accuracy and any grammatical issues. Based on their feedback, the questions were refined and then used in interviews with the participants.

Data analysis

The study applied thematic analysis to the qualitative data collected during the interviews. This process entails analysing verbatim transcripts from the interviews identifying themes and patterns guided by the research question and the selected theoretical frameworks underpinning the study. Data was coded and categorised according to themes that emerged during repetitive reading and transcriptions. A similar method was employed by Mpuangnan (2023) to explore pedagogical strategies for technology integration in basic teacher education programs.

Findings

The findings of the study are presented under three thematic areas such as teachers' perspectives on pace setters' approach to curriculum coverage, teachers' perspectives on pace setters' approach to quality teaching, and teachers' perspectives on pace setters' approach to learners' academic achievement. The details of the findings are presented as follows.

Teachers' perspectives on pace setters' approach to curriculum coverage

Teachers perceive the designated pace set for curriculum coverage as impractical, finding it disconnected from the diverse and dynamic realities of the classroom environment. The study reveals that adhering to the prescribed pace poses challenges for teachers because the actual conditions in the classroom often deviate significantly from the anticipated scenarios envisioned by curriculum designers. These sentiments are reflected in the following comments from participants:

"The pace setter approach often feels too rigid (T4). Sometimes, the time allocated to specific items on the ATP is too little (T1). Say you are to treat essay writing with 250 learners, 61 in a class... That needs more time to treat essay writing because giving them the skill to write an introduction alone needs time (T3). The ATP is too rigid – it has no flexibility... and once the authorities come, they want to see how far you have gone with content coverage (T4). If you are behind, they feel like you are relaxing at work, you are not doing your work properly yet, you have different learners' abilities in class that you are supposed to accommodate (T5)."

Teachers' perspectives on pace setters' approach to quality teaching

The participants revealed that some teachers do not uphold standards of quality teaching at all. They merely highlight certain topics and move on to the next, so that they may be seen to be matching the records they keep that adhere to the ATP. Where this is the case, it is apparent that adhering to administrative demands is more important to the teachers concerned than ensuring learner understanding. The practice has a negative effect on the performance of the learners in the following grades, providing a very weak foundation for the cumulative development of knowledge and understanding. Participants commented as follows:

"Sometimes you find some teachers do highlights on the topic without going deeper into what is to be taught to learners, just because they need the record showing that they did that particular topic (T2). You notice this as the learner progresses from one grade to the next grade because you find that learners know nothing about the previous grade's work (T4). This becomes a challenge for the teacher for the present grade (T1)."

It was evident that pacesetters made it more difficult for schools to provide high-quality instruction and learning by making time frames a priority instead of learner understanding. Thus, they might be impeding the Department of Basic Education's objective of offering high-quality instruction and learning opportunities in classrooms. Participants felt that they should not be compelled to teach specific concepts at a particular time and for a specific duration and that there should be flexibility in the pacesetters.

The time allowed for each topic does not allow teachers to adequately explain concepts and effectively integrate assessment activities into lessons; instead, they rush through concepts, and in many cases ignore sections of work

altogether, focusing only on what will be included in tests and examinations. They also lack the time to use test and exam results to improve teaching and learning. Teachers were not going over test papers, showing learners where they went wrong and helping them to correct their mistakes. Thus, a valuable learning opportunity was lost. Participants had this to say.

“... that we can deliver quality teaching and not just fighting for time, as we are doing (T1). Because what it becomes, we say, ‘I need to finish this topic today so that I can move to the next topic tomorrow (T4).’ I don’t have the time, because I’m following the pacesetters that tell me that in weeks one and two you need to cover all these topics ... and there are longer topics in the ATPs (T3). In term one we are given specific content to teach in stipulated weeks. Now we are fighting for time (T5). You always strive towards finishing the topic for the day because tomorrow you have to do another topic (T2).”

The study also revealed that the pace at which teachers are required to complete the curriculum does not enhance the quality of teaching and learning in classrooms, but rather hinders it. Participants reported that because the time constraints were stringent and did not take the diverse needs of learners into account, they were unable to successfully teach more complicated concepts. It was clear that pace setters hindered the delivery of high-quality teaching and learning in the schools. Therefore, they may be hampering the Department of Basic Education’s goal of providing quality teaching and learning in schools.

Teachers’ perspectives on pace setters’ approach to learners’ academic achievement

The participants indicated that the policy of inclusive education was mitigating the attainment of the pacesetters because the pacesetters were set for learners of standard abilities, not learners with serious learning disabilities. Yet the Department had charged them with providing inclusive education to accommodate learners with learning barriers, participants expressed:

“I find that the pace setter approach can negatively impact learners’ academic achievement because it doesn’t give enough time for students to fully understand the content (T5). The Department always tells us to try and accommodate those slow learners in our class, whereas we were not trained to teach disabled learners (T2). The academic achievement might suffer because they are constantly playing catch-up (T4).”

Many responses re-iterated the gap that exists between the Department’s expectations and the reality on the ground. Teachers could not always adhere to pace setters, as they felt they had to move as directed by learners’ abilities. If learners did not understand a concept, they had to spend time explaining it, and so did not meet pace-setter deadlines. In line with this, participants illustrated:

“There is the plan of what you are expected to do, and there is the reality of the classroom situation (T3). So sometimes my expectation is that I’m going to introduce a topic which will take two lessons, maybe two and a half lessons (T1). When you walk into a classroom and teach, you experience difficulties, and sometimes it will take three to four lessons to cover (T4). As I said, there are no allowances; you have to strictly follow the ATP, and in language, you can’t teach multiple concepts in a lesson (T2). So, you have to focus...you have to do the skill and the development in each topic at a time (T2). I cannot go back and reinforce, to check whether the lesson has been understood, and do further development if it has not been understood (T5). So, I can say I want to do one lesson on adjectives or adverbs but if the content is not understood, how I am going to move on to the next topic (T5)?”

Another participant’s view indicated that learners with disabilities experienced great difficulty in answering essay-type questions. Learners struggled to write essays and did not finish in time. Participant explained:

“Students may perform well in tests that focus on memorization, but their long-term academic achievement is affected because they haven’t truly grasped the concepts (T1). In History, we have source-based questions and essay writing (T3). We have learners who do not finish on time and others cannot even write a minimum of three pages of essays (T4). To accommodate those learners with barriers, I just give them extra time to write, maybe on weekends, especially in Grade 11 class, if it is an SBA exam (T2). Our learners are failing to express themselves using the English language (T5).”

Teachers highlight that the stringent time constraints imposed by pace setters significantly restrict their capacity to address the diverse needs of students. Consequently, educators find it challenging to effectively convey more intricate concepts within the prescribed timeframe. The study underscores the inadequacy of a one-size-fits-all approach to curriculum coverage, emphasizing that it fails to accommodate the varied learning speeds and individual requirements of students. This limitation poses a significant obstacle to the overarching goal of providing a comprehensive and inclusive education.

Interestingly, some participants revealed a preference for a more learner-centred approach, allowing them to move at a pace determined by the students and their abilities. In these cases, teachers felt compelled to either ignore the pace setters entirely or employ a combination of strategies to adapt, sometimes choosing to skip certain sections of the curriculum in order to cope with the challenges posed by rigid timelines. This adaptive approach underscores the importance of flexibility in accommodating diverse learning needs and maintaining student engagement in the learning process.

Discussion of findings

This incongruence highlights the importance of incorporating flexibility into the curriculum implementation process to better accommodate the unique circumstances and needs of individual classrooms (Aini, 2023; Ndari & Mahmudah,

2023). The identified characteristics of the goal-setting theory, particularly the importance of setting actionable goals, align with the findings of the study. According to Locke and Latham's goal-setting theory (2020) and Gross et al. (1971) curriculum implementation theory, the effectiveness of goals is contingent upon their practicality and adaptability to real-world situations. The study supports the premise that a rigidly fixed pace, divorced from the practicalities of the classroom, can hinder rather than improve the teaching and learning process. Therefore, there is a need for a more nuanced and adaptable approach to curriculum design and implementation, one that recognizes and addresses the dynamic nature of the educational environment. This would ensure that teachers can effectively navigate the challenges posed by diverse classroom conditions while maintaining the quality of the teaching and learning experience.

Teachers collectively agree that strict adherence to a predetermined curriculum pace not only fails to enhance but actually hampers the overall quality of teaching and learning. This alignment with established theories, such as Locke's goal-setting theory and Gross et al. (1971) curriculum implementation theory, underscores the crucial relationship between performance and goals. The study highlights a negative correlation between the approach of pacesetters and teachers' effectiveness in conveying complex concepts. The imposition of time constraints, coupled with a lack of consideration for diverse student needs, results in a compromise in the quality of education (Muller & Mildemberger, 2021).

Participants from this openly acknowledge the dilemma they face, caught between adhering to the pace setters and delivering quality teaching. Striking a balance becomes challenging, as strict adherence to predetermined paces compromises the quality of teaching and learning. Conversely, prioritizing quality teaching becomes difficult when trying to keep up with the prescribed pace (Glazzard & Rose, 2020). The study reveals that teachers strictly adhering to the pace setters struggle to provide quality teaching and learning experiences in the classroom, posing a risk of knowledge gaps for all learners. Despite the acknowledged importance of quality teaching in learners' practices, most participating teachers admit to not operationalizing it in their day-to-day classroom activities, as outlined by Garcia, Olsen, and Simbaquebe (2021). According to the goal-setting theory, this failure to operationalize quality teaching leaves teachers without a sense of accomplishment, as the challenging and unactionable goal remains elusive.

The study suggests a connection between the challenges faced by teachers and the policy of inclusive education, where all learners are entitled to the right to learn (Kazihla, 2020). However, the time pressure imposed on teachers often prevents them from dedicating sufficient attention to struggling learners, as the constant demand is to move swiftly to the next topic. Consequently, many slower learners become disengaged, foregoing the opportunity to participate in extra classes offered by teachers to help them catch up. This suggests that the pace-setting approach may unintentionally alienate slower learners from the educational process.

Recommendations

1. This study recommends a curriculum that is adaptable and flexible enough to consider the variety of educational environments. This environment should be created by the Department of Basic Education.
2. Rather than rigidly following a predetermined curriculum, every school ought to be allowed the freedom to map out their curriculum and prioritize subjects based on their unique needs. These conditions include differences in the background as well as discrepancies in the infrastructure and resource availability.
3. Instead of battling with an ideal curriculum that might not match reality, teachers and learners would be better served by working with an adapted curriculum that fits their circumstances.
4. Future researchers should investigate how making pace-setter guidelines more flexible could affect teaching quality and curriculum coverage. Understanding how adjustments to these guidelines might improve classroom experiences and outcomes can provide valuable insights for creating more effective and adaptable teaching strategies

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to investigate and understand teachers' perspectives on various aspects related to the pace setters' approach to curriculum coverage for quality teaching and learning. The research findings indicate that teachers consistently voice their discontent with the mandated pace for completing the curriculum, deeming it impractical. This reflects the goal-setting theory in that the goal should be actionable, achievable and realistic to have the best outcome. A significant challenge arises from their difficulty in adapting to the required teaching and learning pace. Participants encountered difficulties in keeping up with the pace, particularly when dealing with learners of varying learning capabilities.

Teachers revealed that they deviate from the mandated pace and instead take into account the student's comprehension levels. Notably, some teachers adhering strictly to the prescribed pace seemed to focus solely on preparing learners for examinations rather than imparting the comprehensive skills necessary for the learners' overall development. The study brought to light that the prescribed pace for curriculum coverage had adverse effects on the quality of teaching and learning. Many students were left overwhelmed and anxious as they struggled to grasp new concepts within the imposed timeframe.

Furthermore, the research highlighted a significant disparity between the envisioned pace set at the administrative level and the actual classroom practices in schools. This suggests a need for reassessment of the curriculum implementation strategy to ensure a more realistic and effective approach that caters to both teachers and learners.

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